

APPENDIX C – INFORMED CONSENT FORMS

DEVELOPER INFORMED CONSENT FORM (ICF)

Research Title:

Adoption of Blockchain for Decentralized Execution Agreements: Empirical Evidence of Usability and Acceptance

Principal Investigator: <RESEARCHER_NAME OMITTED FOR REVIEW>

Institution: <INSTITUTION OMITTED FOR REVIEW>

Course: Computer Science

Advisor: <ADVISOR_NAME OMITTED FOR REVIEW>

Researcher Contact: <RESEARCHER_EMAIL OMITTED FOR REVIEW>

Research Presentation

You are invited to voluntarily participate in a research study entitled "Adoption of Blockchain for Decentralized Execution Agreements: Empirical Evidence of Usability and Acceptance" which aims to analyze the usability and acceptance when using an experimental blockchain-based application, with a focus on the transparency of administrative processes. This study is part of the Final Course Project (TCC) for the Computer Science course at the <INSTITUTION OMITTED FOR REVIEW>.

Procedures

If you agree to participate, you will be invited to interact with a web application consisting of four endpoints representing the functionalities of the proposed integration. After this interaction, you will be asked to answer a questionnaire containing qualitative and quantitative questions related to usability and overall experience during the activity. Participation will take an estimated 40 minutes.

Risks and Benefits

The risks are minimal and similar to those of common activities performed in a computer environment. Although there are no direct financial benefits, your participation will contribute to the development of more transparent and accessible solutions in public systems.

Confidentiality

The information collected will be used exclusively for academic purposes and kept confidential. No personal or identifiable data will be disclosed, ensuring the anonymity of participants.

Voluntary Participation and Right of Withdrawal

Your participation is voluntary. You may refuse to participate or withdraw at any time, without justification and without prejudice.

Clarifications

If you have any questions, you can contact the researcher responsible by email:
<RESEARCHER_EMAIL OMITTED FOR REVIEW>.

Do you agree with the terms presented?

- I am over 18 years of age and agree to my data being used for the purposes of this research.

END USERS INFORMED CONSENT FORM (ICF)

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